

Overview of ToxHabits at BioCreative IX: corpus, guidelines and evaluation of systems for the detection of Toxic Habits from text

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Abstract

Systems able to detect mentions of substance use and abuse from clinical texts are essential for healthcare analytics, substance use surveillance, and AI-based decision support. Compared to other clinical concepts, substance use and behavioral information are often only captured in free-text narratives and are rarely structured in electronic health records. Despite their relevance for clinical research and public health, few annotated corpora exist for substance use detection, and prior efforts have been limited by narrow domain coverage, English-only datasets, or lack of event-based annotations. To address these limitations, we proposed the ToxHabits shared task. The task is based on a Spanish corpus of 1,499 clinical case reports covering multiple medical specialties, with event-based annotations for substance use and associated attributes. The task is divided into two subtasks: ToxNER, focused on identifying substance use mentions (triggers), and ToxUse, aimed at extracting related information that characterizes the substance use (arguments), such as type, frequency, and route. A total of 6 teams participated, each allowed to submit up to 5 runs per subtask. The top-scoring systems achieved an F1-score of 0.94 for ToxNER and 0.91 for ToxUse. Considering the complexity of real-world narratives, nested entities, and fine-grained event structures, these results demonstrate the viability of accurate substance use detection from clinical text and offer a strong benchmark for future work in Spanish-language biomedical NLP. The ToxHabits Gold Standard is freely available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/15425460>.

Keywords

Substance use detection, Named Entity Recognition, Information Extraction, Clinical case reports, Event-based annotation, Spanish biomedical NLP,

1. Introduction

Substance use disorders pose a significant global public health challenge, affecting millions of individuals and contributing to increased morbidity, mortality, and socioeconomic burden [1]. According to the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) World Drug Report 2023, drug use remains high across the globe: in 2021, approximately 1 in every 17 people aged 15 to 64 had used a drug in the past year. This marks a 23% increase in users from 240 million in 2011 to 296 million in 2021, partly driven by global population growth [2]. It is estimated that around 270 million people worldwide (5.5% of the population aged 15-64) use psychoactive drugs, leading to significant health, social, and economic consequences. About 35 million people are affected by drug use disorders, which are linked to increased risks of morbidity and premature mortality, impaired personal and occupational functioning, and substantial costs to healthcare systems and social services. Globally, drug use accounts for approximately 0.5 million deaths annually-350,000 among men and 150,000 among women. Furthermore, an estimated 11 million people inject drugs, with 1.4 million living with HIV and 5.6 million with hepatitis C [3, 4].

In this context, the accurate detection and characterization of substance use from clinical narratives are crucial for supporting biomedical research, enhancing patient care, and informing evidence-based public health policies [5, 6]. Clinical texts often contain valuable but unstructured information about

Challenge and Workshop (BC9): Large Language Models for Clinical and Biomedical NLP, International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence (IJCAI), August 16–22, 2025, Montreal, Canada

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Figure 1: Overview of the ToxHabits Shared Task pipeline, from input clinical text to trigger and argument extraction.

patients’ substance use behaviors, making automated extraction systems essential tools for leveraging this data effectively.

Unlike structured clinical data such as diagnoses, laboratory results, or medications, detailed information about substance use is often only available in unstructured clinical narratives, including case reports, discharge summaries, and progress notes [7]. Extracting this information automatically requires natural language processing (NLP) methods capable of recognizing mentions of substances and their use characteristics within diverse and complex textual contexts [8, 9].

Despite the importance of this task, existing annotated corpora for substance use detection remain limited, especially for languages other than English [10]. Furthermore, prior datasets typically lack event-based annotation structures that capture nuanced relationships and attributes, such as frequency, duration, and method of consumption associated with substance use instances; this need is underscored by resources like the Social History Annotation Corpus (SHAC), which include precisely those event-based annotations for substance use status, duration, type, and frequency [11].

To address these challenges, we propose the ToxHabits shared task [12], focused on the automatic detection of substance use mentions and their related characteristics from Spanish clinical case reports. The task is divided into two subtasks: **ToxNER**, which involves the identification of substance use mentions framed as a Named Entity Recognition (NER) task, and **ToxUse**, which targets the detection of entities characterizing substance use instances, such as frequency or duration, also framed as an NER task.

This paper presents an overview of the ToxHabits shared task and its resources. The following sections describe the task design, dataset, annotation guidelines, and evaluation methodology. We then summarize participation statistics, system results, and discuss key findings and challenges observed during the competition. Finally, we highlight potential directions for future research in substance use detection from clinical narratives.

2. Task Description

2.1. Shared Task Description

The ToxHabits shared task aims to advance the automatic extraction of substance use information from unstructured Spanish clinical narratives. Participants were challenged to identify mentions of substances (e.g., alcohol, tobacco, cannabis) and extract associated contextual attributes such as frequency, duration, and method of use. Departing from prior efforts, ToxHabits adopts a fine-grained, event-based annotation framework that supports detailed modeling of substance use behavior (see Fig. 1).

The task is grounded in the ToxHabits corpus, a manually annotated gold-standard dataset comprising 1,499 clinical case reports across multiple medical specialties [12]. Annotations were produced by domain experts following an event-centric schema inspired by the SHAC corpus from the n2c2/UW Social Determinants of Health (SDoH) 2022 shared task, capturing structured relationships between substances and their attributes rather than isolated entity spans or normalized concepts. The corpus is further described in Section 3.1.

System outputs were evaluated against gold annotations using micro-averaged precision, recall, and F1-score. Each team could submit up to five runs per sub-task.

2.2. Sub-tasks

ToxHabits is organized into two Spanish-language sub-tasks, both formulated as sequence labeling tasks:

- **Sub-task 1 (ToxNER):** In this sub-task, participants must detect the spans that act as **Triggers** for substance use events. Each trigger must be classified into one of the four predefined categories: *Tobacco*, *Alcohol*, *Cannabis*, or *Drug* (used for other substances such as cocaine, heroin, etc.). The goal is to accurately identify the textual expressions that indicate an episode of substance use in clinical texts.
- **Sub-task 2 (ToxUse):** In this sub-task, participants must identify and classify the **Arguments** associated with each detected trigger. There are six argument types, each providing contextual information about the substance use. The possible argument types are Type, Method, Amount, Frequency, Duration and History.

While the corpus annotations include relations between triggers and arguments, due to time constraints this sub-task focuses exclusively on the detection and classification of argument spans, without requiring participants to establish explicit links between them and their corresponding triggers.

Unlike many prior shared tasks, ToxHabits does not include an entity normalization component, focusing exclusively on high-quality detection and categorization of text spans relevant to substance use.

2.3. Evaluation

System performance for both sub-tasks was assessed by comparing participant outputs against the expert-annotated gold standard. The evaluation conducted using established metrics to ensure a fair and consistent comparison of results across all submissions.

For Sub-task 1 (ToxNER), the primary evaluation metric was the *exact-match micro-averaged precision, recall, and F1-score*, where a prediction is considered correct only if both the span boundaries and the entity type exactly match those in the gold standard. For Sub-task 2 (ToxUse), the same evaluation strategy was applied to the argument spans. These metrics are calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Precision } (P) &= \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Positives}} \\ \text{Recall } (R) &= \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Negatives}} \\ \text{F1 score } (F1) &= \frac{2 * (P * R)}{(P + R)} \end{aligned}$$

An official evaluation script was provided to ensure reproducibility and consistency. The script, along with detailed usage instructions, are made publicly available on GitHub¹

3. Corpus and Resources

3.1. ToxHabits Gold Standard

The ToxHabits Gold Standard is a collection of 1,499 clinical case reports in Spanish annotated with instances of substance use and abuse. The texts were annotated by clinical experts using dedicated

¹https://github.com/nlp4bia-bsc/ToxHabits_evaluation_library

annotation guidelines inspired by the Social History Annotation Corpus (SHAC) [11]. The dataset is split into training and testing, with 1,199 documents being used for training and 300 for testing (See Table 1). The texts in the corpus were manually chosen from a larger collection of clinical case reports due to their relevance to the corpus. They belong to different clinical specialties, with a special focus on psychiatry-related cases due to a higher concentration of drug-related content.

Table 1

Number of annotated instances in the ToxHabits dataset divided by labels.

Dataset	Class	Train	Test	Total
ToxNER	Drug	4,686	1,086	5,772
	Alcohol	1,280	375	1,655
	Tobacco	833	215	1,048
	Cannabis	793	162	955
	Total	7,592	1,838	9,430
ToxUse	Type	3,818	917	4,735
	Duration	1,654	395	2,049
	Frequency	1,543	414	1,957
	Amount	1,330	390	1,720
	Method	724	171	895
	History	459	101	560
	Total	9,528	2,388	11,916
Overall Total		17,120	4,226	21,346

The corpus uses an event-based structure to annotate and characterize substance use and abuse. There are four different possible event triggers: *Tobacco*, *Alcohol*, *Cannabis*, and *Drug*. Each event can be then characterized by arguments of six possible types:

- **Type:** The specific substance used. *Example:* “*cocaína*” (cocaine), “*heroína*” (heroin)
- **Method:** The way the substance was used. *Example:* “*fumada*” (smoked), “*inyectada*” (injected)
- **Amount:** The quantity of substance used. *Example:* “*dos cervezas*” (two beers), “*un paquete al día*” (a pack per day)
- **Frequency:** The regularity of substance use. *Example:* “*cada fin de semana*” (every weekend), “*a diario*” (daily)
- **Duration:** The time span over which the substance was used. *Example:* “*durante cinco años*” (for five years), “*desde los 15 años*” (since age 15)
- **History:** The point in time when substance use ceased. *Example:* “*dejado en 2007*” (quit in 2007), “*abandonó el consumo hace un año*” (stopped using a year ago)

In addition to these six, there is an additional argument type named *StatusType*. This argument is used to annotate the temporality and assertion status of the event. In addition to the text span, it has an associated subtype label, which can be either *Current*, *Past*, *None* or *AWSE* (Associated with Someone Else). The only compulsory argument type is *StatusType*, with the others being dependent on their appearance in the text. Each event may have more than one argument of the same type, and each sentence may have more than one event. Figure 2 shows two different annotated events.

Each event trigger is associated with its respective arguments using relations to form a complete event structure. Although for the shared task only annotated text spans were used, it is planned to release the complete event-based annotation in the future.

The corpus was annotated by two experts in Biology, under the supervision of a senior annotator with a clinical background. Specific guidelines were created for the annotation. Using the SHAC Corpus [11] guidelines as a starting point, around 10% of the corpus was annotated in multiple rounds in which the ToxHabits guidelines were iteratively improved upon with new rules and examples. The final

Figure 2: Example of two annotated events of the ToxHabits corpus. Translation: *51-year-old man with past history of multi-drug consumption. Nowadays, (he takes) 1-2 g/day of cannabis orally.*

Table 2

Overview of the teams that participated in ToxHabits. In the Affiliation column, A/I stands for academic or industry institution.

Team Name	Affiliation	Tasks	Ref.
NOWJ	VNU, University of Engineering and Technology, Vietnam [A]	NER, Use	[13]
SINAI	University of Jaen, Spain [A]	NER, Use	[14]
FMI-SU	Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridski, Bulgaria [A], Graphwise [I]	NER	[15]
ICB-UMA	University of Malaga, Spain [A]	NER, Use	[16]
Orekhovichi	Institute of Biomedical Chemistry, Moscow, Russia [A]	NER, Use	[17]
GooseSeek	University of North Texas, USA [A]	NER, Use	-

inter-annotator agreement (calculated as the pairwise agreement between the two main annotators) was of 0.948 for triggers and 0.832 for arguments.

The final version of the guidelines is freely available online in Spanish on Zenodo². They are 47-pages long and contain a total of 68 rules for the annotation of drug use and abuse using an event structure. In addition, they also contain recommendations for the linking of some argument types to the controlled vocabulary SNOMED CT.

4. Task Results

4.1. Participation Overview

A total of six teams from five different countries participated in the shared task. Five of these teams submitted to both ToxNER and ToxUse, while one team submitted only to the ToxNER task. Each team was allowed to submit up to five entries per subtask. In total, we received 19 submissions for ToxNER and 14 submissions for ToxUse. Table 2 shows the complete list of participating teams, along with their affiliation and the reference to their task paper.

4.2. Results and Methodologies

The complete results for Sub-task 1 (ToxNER) are shown in Table 3, while the results for Sub-task 2 (ToxUse) are shown in Table 4 and a summary of the presented approaches is in Table 5.

The top-performing team, **NOWJ** [13], designed an ensemble model to handle both subtasks at once. Instead of treating them separately, they turned the whole problem into a BIO-style token classification task, using BETO model [18] with a Conditional Random Field (CRF) layer to tag sequences. Then, as post-processing, they used a BERT-based classifier to filter out irrelevant sentences. They also trained multiple models on different resampled versions of the data and combined their outputs through

²<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15753952>

Table 3

Submissions to the ToxNER Shared Task, ranked by F1-score. The best result is bolded, and the second-best is underlined.

Team Name	Run Name	Precision	Recall	F1
NOWJ	2-full-train-filtered-triggers	<i>0.94</i>	<i>0.94</i>	0.94
NOWJ	5-full-train-filtered-different-parameters-triggers	0.97	0.92	0.94
NOWJ	1-full-train-triggers	0.92	0.95	<i>0.93</i>
SINAI	sinai-toxner	0.89	0.89	0.89
ICB-UMA	6_span_marker_bsc_bio_ehr_es	0.83	0.85	0.84
NOWJ	3-partial-train-triggers	0.83	0.85	0.84
NOWJ	4-partial-train-filtered-triggers	0.83	0.85	0.84
ICB-UMA	7_span_marker_ensemble	0.78	0.87	0.82
ICB-UMA	8_span_marker_roberta_base	0.82	0.80	0.81
ICB-UMA	4_bio_ensemble	0.76	0.84	0.80
ICB-UMA	5_bio_span_marker_ensemble	0.72	<i>0.91</i>	0.80
GooseSeek	submission_taks1	0.87	0.72	0.79
Orekhovichi	1-ToxNER-bert-optim	0.83	0.65	0.73
FMI-SU	3-gpt-4.1-fewshot	0.59	0.72	0.65
FMI-SU	1-dictionary-baseline	0.46	0.87	0.60
FMI-SU	2-gpt-4.1-zeroshot	0.49	0.68	0.57
FMI-SU	4-dictionary-gpt-4.1-zeroshot	0.43	0.83	0.57
FMI-SU	5-dictionary-gpt-4.1-fewshot	0.44	0.83	0.57
Orekhovichi	2-ToxNER-LLM	0.57	0.36	0.44

Table 4

Submissions to the ToxUse Shared Task, ranked by F1-score. The best result is bolded, and the second-best is underlined.

Team Name	Run Name	Precision	Recall	F1
NOWJ	1-full-train-arguments	0.91	0.9	0.91
NOWJ	2-full-train-filtered-arguments	<i>0.92</i>	<i>0.88</i>	<i>0.90</i>
NOWJ	5-full-train-different-parameters-arguments	0.95	0.85	<i>0.90</i>
SINAI	sinai-toxuse.tsv	0.78	0.79	0.78
NOWJ	3-partial-train-arguments	0.78	0.75	0.77
NOWJ	4-partial-train-filtered-arguments	0.79	0.75	0.77
ICB-UMA	7_span_marker_ensemble.tsv	0.73	0.77	0.75
ICB-UMA	8_span_marker_roberta_base	0.76	0.72	0.74
ICB-UMA	4_bio_ensemble.tsv	0.65	0.80	0.72
ICB-UMA	5_bio_span_marker_ensemble.tsv	0.61	0.84	0.71
ICB-UMA	6_span_marker_bsc_bio_ehr_es.tsv	0.61	0.84	0.71
GooseSeek	submission_task2.tsv	0.75	0.66	0.70
Orekhovichi	1-ToxUse-bert-optim	0.47	0.60	0.53
Orekhovichi	2-ToxUse-LLM	0.38	0.26	0.31

majority voting. This setup worked well and gave the highest results: 0.94 F1 for ToxNER and 0.91 for ToxUse.

The **SINAI** team [14] followed a more mixed approach, combining transformers fine-tuned for domain-specific tasks with generative models. For ToxNER, they used EuroBERT model [19], which is optimized for European languages and can handle long texts. For ToxUse, they started by running their NER system to find substances, then used TF-IDF to retrieve similar training examples. Finally, they applied an instruction-tuned large language model with a few-shot prompt to extract more context. This approach worked well for the complexity and sparsity of Spanish clinical data.

The **ICB-UMA** team [16] tested two kinds of models: the traditional BIO-based taggers and span-based models that look at chunks of text. They fine-tuned a Spanish biomedical RoBERTa model [20] for both approaches. In their experiments, the span-based models outperformed the BIO ones, especially in

harder cases. They also experimented with ensemble methods like soft voting to boost reliability. In the end, their approach did well overall, with F1 scores of 0.84 for ToxNER and 0.75 for ToxUse.

The **Orekhovichi** team [17] presented two approaches: a supervised BERT-CRF model with data augmentation and hyperparameter tuning, and a zero-shot method using the DeepSeek API. The BERT-based system outperformed the zero-shot approach, highlighting the effectiveness of fine-tuned models in low-resource clinical NLP tasks.

The **FMI-SU** team [15] focused only on ToxNER and tried something different: few-shot prompting with GPT-4.1. They split clinical reports into shorter chunks and built prompts using five sample annotations from the training set. GPT-4.1 then returned structured outputs to identify toxic habits. While the results were promising, F1 of 0.65, they ran into issues with fuzzy entity boundaries and extra context being included—like negation cues that were not part of the target entity.

Finally, the **GooseSeek** team used a pre-trained Spanish biomedical transformer (roberta-base-biomedical-clinical-es) fine-tuned using the task data. They used a weighted cross-entropy loss function to address class imbalance, and leveraged the Hugging Face Trainer API, with dynamic adjustment of class weights to improve minority class recall. These settings achieved a 0.79 F1-score for the ToxNER subtask and 0.70 for the ToxUse subtask.

Table 5

Summary of team approaches and techniques for the shared task.

Team	Short Summary of Approach	Technique Name
NOWJ	Unified both subtasks into BIO token classification with BETO+CRF, added BERT-based filtering, resampled ensembles with majority voting.	BETO+CRF Ensemble
SINAI	Combined EuroBERT NER for substances, TF-IDF retrieval, and instruction-tuned LLM few-shot prompting for context extraction.	EuroBERT + LLM Few-Shot
ICB-UMA	Compared BIO-based vs. span-based tagging using Spanish biomedical RoBERTa; span-based performed better; used soft voting ensemble.	Span-based RoBERTa Ensemble
Orekhovichi	Supervised BERT-CRF with data augmentation & tuning vs. zero-shot DeepSeek API; supervised model won.	BERT-CRF + Data Augmentation
FMI-SU	Few-shot prompting with GPT-4.1 on chunked reports using sample annotations; structured outputs for toxic habit NER.	GPT-4.1 Few-Shot Prompting
GooseSeek	Fine-tuned Spanish biomedical RoBERTa with weighted cross-entropy & dynamic class weights for imbalance handling.	Weighted RoBERTa Fine-Tuning

5. Discussion

In summary, this paper has introduced the ToxHabits shared task as a new benchmark for Spanish-language clinical NLP, specifically targeting the extraction of substance use information with event-based annotations. Participation in the ToxHabits shared task was robust, with 6 teams submitting a total of 20 runs per task. The highest achieved F1-scores were 0.94 for ToxNER and 0.91 for ToxUse, reflecting the task’s complexity and the efficacy of the proposed approaches. The approaches submitted to the ToxHabits Shared Task reflect not only the maturity of established NER techniques but also the inherent difficulty of the task. Systems that modeled both subtasks jointly, using BIO tagging combined with CRF decoding and ensemble strategies, consistently delivered the strongest results. These designs used best practices data preparation, such as data resampling and filtering irrelevant content, that contributed better predictions. Other submissions explored hybrid designs, fusing transformer-based NER models with retrieval and prompting components. While these methods showed promise, particularly in capturing richer context—they generally lagged behind end-to-end supervised systems in accuracy.

Approaches based on prompt-engineering using general purpose Large Language Models were less competitive overall. Despite the appeal of few-shot learning, these systems struggled with precise entity boundary detection and they were sensitive to prompt design. Zero-shot results were notably lower, underscoring the limitations of off-the-shelf models in specialized clinical tasks.

In sum, fine-tuned supervised models remain the most reliable choice for clinical entity extraction in low-resource languages.

6. Funding

The ToxHabits track was funded by Spanish and European projects such as DataTools4Heart (Grant Agreement No. 101057849), AI4HF (Grant Agreement No. 101080430). This publication is part of the R &D &I project TED2021-129974B-C22, funded by MICIU/AEI /10.13039 /501100011033 and by the European Union NextGenerationEU/PRTR (BARITONE (Proyectos de Transición Ecológica y Transición Digital 2021)).

Declaration on Generative AI

During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used OpenAI-GPT-4.1 in order to: enhance grammar and spelling check. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the publication's content.

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